

PATRIOTISM IS THE BASIS OF OUR NATIONAL IDEA

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Abstract: the historical heritage of our people is of great importance in the education of patriots. Therefore, the preservation, study and transfer of historical heritage to future generations has become one of the priorities of our state's policy.

This article explores the concept of patriotism and its important aspects in the development of society.

Keywords: Patriotism, national idea, civil society, modernization, military patriotism, sense of Homeland.

VATANPARVARLIK – MILLIY G‘OYAMIZ ASOSI

Annotatsiya: Vatanparvar insonlarni tarbiyalashda xalqimizning tarixiy merosi katta ahamiyatga ega. Shu sababli tarixiy merosni asrab-avaylash, o‘rganish va kelajak avlodlarga qoldirish davlatimiz siyosatining ustivor yo‘nalishlaridan biriga aylandi.

Ushbu maqolada vatanparvarlik tushunchasi va uning jamiyat taraqqiyotidagi muhim jihatlari tadqiq etilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: vatanparvarlik, milliy g‘oya, fuqarolik jamiyati, modernizatsiya, harbiy vatanparvarlik, vatan tuyg‘usi.

ПАТРИОТИЗМ – ОСНОВА НАШЕЙ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ИДЕИ

Аннотация: большое значение в воспитании патриотов имеет историческое наследие нашего народа. Поэтому сохранение, изучение и передача исторического наследия будущим поколениям стало одним из приоритетов политики нашего государства.

В этой статье исследуется концепция патриотизма и его важные аспекты в развитии общества.

Ключевые слова: Патриотизм, национальная идея, гражданское общество, модернизация, военный патриотизм, чувство Родины.

INTRODUCTION

Patriotic education of young people is an important issue for all of us, which never loses its relevance and significance. This topical issue is a continuous process consisting of a complex of interrelated political and legal, socio-economic, ideological and ideological, cultural and educational activities. Today, work on military-patriotic education of young people is carried out in accordance with the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decisions of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decrees and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, resolutions and orders of the Cabinet of Ministers, general military charters of the Armed Forces and other legislative acts.

Patriotic education, being an integral part of the general educational process, is a systematic and purposeful activity of state authorities and public organizations to form a high patriotic consciousness among citizens, a sense of loyalty to their Fatherland, readiness to fulfill civic duty and constitutional duties to protect the interests of the Motherland.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

The successful solution of the tasks of strengthening the defense capability of countries is inextricably linked with the education of young people, increasing their political consciousness, labor activity, accelerating scientific and technological progress.

Education is an objectively natural process of preparing people for work or other useful activities in society, to perform diverse social functions. Methods of education are ways of interaction between teachers and pupils aimed at achieving educational objectives. Methods of education involve active interaction between the teacher and the pupil.

The great educator Abdullah Avlony said: "Science is the value of the world. Knowledge is the highest and sacred property of man. For knowledge, like a mirror, shows us our worldview, our aspirations: like a sword, it sharpens our mind, our thought."

Our ancestors developed a set of criteria for the moral assessment of a person, in modern terms, created the "eastern moral code". In the soul of a person there must live an irreconcilability towards those who earn their bread dishonestly, to dishonesty, to injustice.

Only such a person always keeps his word, does not encroach on someone else's good, will not spare his life in the name of the people and his Homeland, and, conversely, a lying windbag does not have a sense of patriotism. Any dark and wrong deed, selfishness, self-interest, so that they do not dress up is a betrayal of the Motherland.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Educating young people in the military-patriotic spirit is a multi — stage, systematic, purposeful and coordinated activity of state bodies, public associations and other organizations aimed at forming a sense of loyalty to the motherland in young people, regardless of nationality, language and profession, educating them as individuals capable of fulfilling their civil duty and constancy obligations, protecting the interests of society andIn the concept of educating young people in the spirit of military-patriotism, the stages and directions of military-patriotic are clearly and clearly outlined. Accordingly, military-patriotic education and education are carried out in a harmonious manner in the following four stages:

The first stage (3-7 years old) is considered a stage in which initial perceptions of the surrounding world, Homeland appear, which includes teaching children various poems, melodies and songs in family and preschool organizations, showing cartoons and various games, understanding the world by drawing pictures, forming love for the mother-country in them based on acquaintance with state symbols (flag, coat of arms, anthem).

At the second stage (7-16 years old), students are invited to strengthen love and devotion to the Motherland, fulfill their children's duty to the Motherland with high responsibility, expand their positive ideas about our Armed Forces, increase the prestige of military service, form physically healthy, spiritually mature, broad worldviews, independent thinking personalities among young people.

At the third stage (16-18 years old), young people are directed to ensure spiritual and physical readiness for a worthy service to the motherland and its protection. It will be detailed about the need for physically strong and spiritually mature youth for our national army, the importance of military service, the reforms carried out in the Armed Forces.

The fourth stage (ages 18-30) implies the development of the physical and spiritual abilities of young people, leadership skills and intellectual potential, general and professional qualifications, their regular work on themselves, motivation to live a healthy life and achieving it.

The concept of military-patriotic education of youth – developed on the basis of the basic principles and priorities of the state youth policy implemented in the country, current tasks and ways to solve them related to the education of youth in the spirit of military-patriotic education in the current complex globalization, rapid development of information and communication

technologies, the work of state and non-governmental organizations, families, mahalla, education determines the role and importance of institutions, their interaction in this matter, taking into account national and international legal norms.

In this Concept, the issue of military-patriotic education of young people is considered as an integral and integral part of an integral educational system related to the upbringing of a physically healthy generation, in accordance with the requirements of the action strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, combined with advanced national and international experience, real socio-political changes in life today's Uzbekistan. separately, attention is paid to the issue of improvement. Важный принцип патриотической работы - единство патриотического и интернационального воспитания.

The organic interrelation and interdependence of patriotic and international tasks in the activities of all educators act as a powerful factor shaping the personality of a warrior, constantly reminding that he protects and in the name of which he took up arms.

Patriotism is love and loyalty to Uzbekistan, its history, national, cultural and spiritual values.

Training plays a leading role in the formation of both value and intellectual components of military-patriotic consciousness.

However, this theoretical conclusion, which does not cause objections, is not fully implemented in the practice of teachers teaching the basics of sciences.

Teachers of general education subjects rather superficially represent the tasks of military-patriotic education and the opportunities that the disciplines they teach have in solving these tasks.

The content and process of military-patriotic education at the present stage should be enriched with trends that are conditioned by the acquisition of independence, the true sovereignty of the Republic, the restructuring of the school, the increasing role of the human factor in accelerating the socio-economic development of the country, the protection of the Fatherland, cardinal changes in the organization of military labor.

The restructuring of the work on preparing young people for the defense of the Motherland requires a fuller use of both the substantive side of military-patriotic education and organizational and methodological. It is necessary to analyze the effectiveness of educational measures, the selection and consolidation of traditional forms put forward and proven by the practice of military-patriotic work, the search for fundamentally new ones that in modern conditions most fully realize the tasks of preparing students for the defense of the fatherland.

CONCLUSION

Readiness to defend the Motherland cannot be considered only as a consequence of special mass defense work, military sports games and other undoubtedly important forms of mass military education. It is a natural result of the comprehensive development of students' personalities, their assimilation of all the riches of social culture. And when we talk about a healthy person, we mean not only physical health, but we mean a person with strong moral and ethical standards, brought up in the spirit of the best universal ideals.

Preparation for the defense of the Motherland at this age takes place in the sphere of self-awareness, self-education of schoolchildren. They get a complete picture of the moral standard, the ideal of a human worker and defender of the Motherland.

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